

Kinetics and mechanism of the ligand substitution reaction of $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2\text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ {tap = 2-(*m*-tolylazo)pyridine} with diethyldithiocarbamate anion in aqueous solution at pH 7.4

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Abstract : Kinetic and mechanistic studies on the interaction of diethyldithiocarbamate anion [DDTC⁻] with the title complex at physiological pH and in aqueous medium have been done spectrophotometrically as a function of $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2\text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$, [DDTC⁻], pH and temperature at constant ionic strength. The interaction reaction followed two parallel paths : both the paths are dependent on [ligand] and showed a limiting nature at higher concentration of the ligand. Rate constants ($k_1 \sim 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_2 \sim 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$), activation parameters ($\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 14.14 \pm 0.96 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -241.59 \pm 2.93 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 31.88 \pm 1.91 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -232.94 \pm 5.79 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) were calculated. A rate law involving the outer sphere association complex formation has been established at pH 7.4 as

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 K_E \{[(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2\text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}\} [\text{ligand}] / (1 + K_E [\text{ligand}])$$

Based on the kinetic and activation parameters an associative interchange mechanism is proposed for the interaction processes. From the temperature dependence of the outer sphere association equilibrium constant, the thermodynamic parameters were also calculated, which gives a negative ΔG° value for both the paths at all temperatures studied, supporting the spontaneous formation of an outer sphere association complex. The product of the reaction has been characterized, as IR and ESI-mass spectroscopic analysis.

Keywords : Ru^{II}, diethyldithiocarbamate, kinetics, pH 7.4, aqueous medium.

Introduction

The studies¹⁻⁵ on the bioactivity and the DNA-binding capability of Ru^{II/III} complexes are emerging as an interesting area because of their lower toxicity compared to platinum complexes, such as cisplatin, carboplatin and others. Cisplatin⁶ and carboplatin⁷ are well known drugs for cancer chemotherapy, but certain tumors are resistant to them and furthermore platinum complexes can also induce toxic effects. Different studies reveal that a number ruthenium compounds serve as bacterial mutagens and are capable of damaging genetic material⁸⁻¹². A series of ruthenium complexes exhibit antitumour¹³⁻¹⁶, anticancer¹⁷, antileukemic¹⁸, anti-HIV¹⁹ and antifungal activity^{20,21}.

The ligand sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDTC) has been investigated as a biochemical modulator of the toxicity associated with clinically used cancer chemothera-

peutic agents²². The effect of diethyldithiocarbamate anion [DDTC⁻] of chelating Zn inhibits metallo-proteinases, which in turn prevents the degradation of extracellular matrix, which is an initial step in cancer metastasis and angiogenesis²³.

The aim of the present work is to study the complex formation of diethyldithiocarbamate [DDTC] anion with the title complex in aqueous medium, where ruthenium(II), which is a pro-drug, is stable even at biological pH 7.4 due to the presence of the strong pi-acceptor ligand tap {2-(*m*-tolylazo)pyridine}²⁴.

Experimental

The compound *cis*-diaqua-bis-{2-(*m*-tolylazo)pyridine} ruthenium(II) diperchlorate, monohydrate, *cis*-[Ru(tap)₂(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₂·H₂O and the reacting complex ion $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2\text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ (1) was prepared

following the methods described earlier^{25,26}. The product $[(\text{tap})_2\text{Ru}(\mu\text{-O})(\mu\text{-DDTC})\text{Ru}(\text{tap})_2]^+$ (**2**) of the reaction between complex (**1**) and $[\text{DDTC}^-]$ was prepared by mixing the reactants in different ratios, specifically 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 5, 1 : 10 and thermostated at 50 °C for 72 h. The spectrum of (**2**) (Fig. 1) shows good complexation between $[\text{DDTC}^-]$ and (**1**). The composition of (**2**) in solution was determined by the Job's method of continuous variation and the metal : ligand ratio was found to be 2 : 1 (Fig. 2). The pH of the solution was adjusted by adding $\text{NaOH}/\text{HClO}_4$ and the measurements were carried out with the help of a Sartorius digital pH meter (PB 11) with an accuracy of ± 0.01 unit. Doubly distilled water was used to prepare all the kinetic solutions. All chemicals used were of AR grade available commercially. The

reactions were carried out at constant ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO_4 .

The IR spectrum of the product in the KBr disk showed prominent band at 1092 cm^{-1} and 382 cm^{-1} . The $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching frequency of the non bonded $[\text{DDTC}^-]$ occurs at 1132 cm^{-1} which shifted 41 cm^{-1} downwards to 1092 cm^{-1} indicating the coordination of the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ group to Ru^{2+} through the S atom of $\text{C}=\text{S}$ group. The two S atoms of the ligand $[\text{DDTC}^-]$ are nonequivalent²⁷. The IR spectra of free ligand displays a sharp peak near $\sim 2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to free -SH group but there is no peak at near $\sim 2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (stretching frequency of free -SH group) in the final product complex. So we can say both S atoms of the ligand involved in bonding. The band at 382 cm^{-1} is therefore assigned to Ru-S stretching frequency.

From the ESI-mass spectra of the product, it is clear that the peak at $m/z \sim 635$ has become the molecular ion species in the mixture solution and this is tentatively attributed to $[\text{DDTC}^-] + 2\text{Ru}^{\text{II}} + 1\text{O}^{2-} + 4\text{tap} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{Na}^+)^{2+}$. The precursor ion is shown in the following :

Fig. 1. Difference in spectrum between complex 1 and product complex 2 : $[\text{I}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DDTC}^-] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 7.4$, cell used 1 cm quartz.

Fig. 2. Job's plot of complex (**1**) with $[\text{DDTC}^-]$.

Plausible structure of the molecular ion peak from the ESI-mass spectra

Kinetics :

Kinetic measurements were carried out on a Shimadzu UV 1601 spectrophotometer attached to a thermoelectric cell temperature controller (model TCC 240A, accuracy $\pm 0.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The conventional mixing technique was followed and pseudo-first order conditions were employed throughout. The progress of the reaction was monitored by measuring the decrease in absorbance at 560 nm, where

Fig. 3. ESI-mass spectra of [DDTC⁻] substituted product.

the difference in spectra between the substrate and the product complex is maximum. The plots of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ against time t , where A_t and A_∞ are the absorbance at time t and at infinite time (after the completion of the reaction) were found to be non-linear; being curved at the initial stage and subsequently of constant slope (Fig. 4). The rate constants for two consecutive steps were calculated using the Weyh and Hamm method²⁸. From

the linear second portion, $k_{2(\text{obs})}$ values were obtained. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values were available from the plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus time. A typical plot is shown in Fig. 5. The rate data represented as an average of duplicate runs were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Results and discussion

First acid dissociation equilibrium of the complex

Fig. 4. A typical plot of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time.

Fig. 5. A typical plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus time.

$[\text{Ru}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ is 6.6^{29} at 25°C . At pH 7.4, the complex ion exists in dimeric oxo-bridged form, $[(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2\text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ $^{30-33}$. At pH 7.4, the mononuclear species exists in the hydroxo-aqua form. Two such species assemble to form the dinuclear oxo-bridged diaqua complex due to thermodynamic force mainly arising from pi-bonding 34 (O^{2-} donor, Ru^{II} acceptor) which is favorable for $4d$ ion, Ru^{II} . Now, such strong covalency reduces the acidity of the coordinated water. The oxo-bridge formation is solely dependent on pH. Electrochemical studies show that there is pH potential domain, where the μ -oxo structures stay intact. Variable temperature study does not show any effect, which is in line with the fact that oxo-bridge formation is solely pH-dependent 35,36 .

The $\text{p}K_a$ value of the ligand sodium diethyldithiocarbamate is 3.37 at 25°C 37 , so that at pH 7.4, the major species involved in the kinetic process is the anionic form of the ligand which is $[\text{DDTC}^-]$. At constant temperature, pH (7.4) and fixed concentration of complex (1) the

$\ln (A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time (t) plot for different ligand concentration indicates a two step process. Both are dependent on the incoming ligand concentration, and with increasing ligand concentration a limiting rate is reached. Job's method of complexation indicates a 2 : 1 metal-ligand ratio in the product complex. This is possible only when the reaction occur parallel path. The rate constant for such process can be evaluated by assuming the following Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

In the starting complex there are two equivalent ruthenium(II) centers. Now the ligand has two donor centers. During the ligation two donor centers attack in two parallel speeds (k_1 and k_2) which is shown in the mechanism and conclusion section.

Calculation of k_1 value :

The rate constant for this path was calculated from the absorbance data using the Weyh and Hamm equation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (A_t - A_\infty) = & \\
 & a_1 \exp(-k_1(\text{obs}) t) + a_2 \exp(-k_2(\text{obs}) t) \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

where a_1 and a_2 are constants that depend upon the rate constants and extinction coefficients.

Values of $a_2 \exp(-k_2(\text{obs}) t)$ at different times (when t is small) were obtained from the linear portion of the curve extended to t equals zero, i.e.

$$a_2 \exp(-k_2(\text{obs}) t) = (A_t - A_\infty)_{\text{limiting}}$$

Therefore values of $(A_t - A_\infty) - a_2 \exp(-k_2(\text{obs}) t)$ were calculated from X-Y (Fig. 4) values at different t ;

$$\Delta = a_1 \exp(-k_1(\text{obs}) t)$$

or,

$$\ln \Delta = \text{constant} - k_1(\text{obs}) t \quad (2)$$

$k_{1(\text{obs})}$ was then derived from the slope of $\ln \Delta$ versus time, when for small values of t (Fig. 5).

A similar procedure was applied for each DDTC anion concentration in the 1.0×10^{-3} to 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} range using the experimental conditions specified in Table 1. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values are collected in Table 1.

Table 1. $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) values for different $[\text{DDTC}^-]$ concentrations at different temperatures

$[\text{Complex}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , pH = 7.4, ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaClO_4

$10^3 \times [\text{Ligand}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)			
	50	55	60	65
1.0	0.81	1.14	1.40	1.79
2.0	1.53	2.08	2.5	3.03
3.0	2.13	2.77	3.45	4.16
4.0	2.50	3.22	4.0	4.76
5.0	2.76	3.85	4.35	5.55

The rate increases with increase in $[\text{ligand}]$ and reaches a limiting value (Fig. 6). The limiting rate constant is probably due to the completion of outer sphere associa-

Fig. 6. Plot of $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ versus $[\text{ligand}]$, A = 50° , B = 55° , C = 60° and D = 65° $^\circ\text{C}$.

tion complex formation. Since the metal ion reacts with its immediate environment, further change in $[\text{ligand}]$ beyond the saturation point will not affect the reaction rate. The outer sphere association complex may be stabilized through H-bonding. Based on the experimental findings, the following Scheme 2 may be proposed for the path (1) \rightarrow (2) (k_1 path);

Based on the above scheme a rate expression can be derived.

$$\begin{aligned}
 d[2]/dt &= \\
 k_1 K_E [\{ (\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2 \text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2 (\text{H}_2\text{O}) \}^{2+}] [\text{DDTC}^-] & \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

or,

$$\begin{aligned}
 d[2]/dt &= \\
 k_{1(\text{obs})} [\{ (\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{tap})_2 \text{RuORu}(\text{tap})_2 (\text{H}_2\text{O}) \}^{2+}]_T & \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

where T stands for total concentration of Ru^{II} . We can then write,

$$k_{1(\text{obs})} = k_1 K_E [\text{DDTC}^-] / (1 + K_E [\text{DDTC}^-]) \quad (5)$$

where k_1 is the rate constant, i.e. the rate constant for the interchange of outer sphere complex to the inner sphere complex; K_E is the outer sphere association equilibrium constant.

The equation can be represented as :

$$1/k_{1(\text{obs})} = 1/k_1 + 1/k_1 K_E [\text{DDTC}^-] \quad (6)$$

The plot of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ against $1/[\text{DDTC}^-]$ should be linear with an intercept of $1/k_1$ and slope $1/k_1 K_E$. This was found to be the case at all temperatures studied. The k_1 and K_E' values were calculated from the intercept and slope (Fig. 7) and are collected in Table 3.

Calculation of k_2 value :

The rate constants for this path were calculated from the latter linear portions of the graphs and are collected in Table 2. This is again dependent on $[\text{DDTC}^-]$ and shows a limiting value at higher ligand concentrations (Fig. 10). The intermediate here is also possibly stable through H-bonding between coordinated water and the approaching DDTC ion. In a parallel reaction two paths overlap each other. But during the calculation of the first path ($k_1 \sim 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$) the contribution from second path ($k_2 \sim 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$) is negligible. On the other hand, when we are calculating the rate constant for the second path the first

Fig. 7. Plot of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ against $1/[\text{ligand}]$, A = 50°, B = 55°, C = 60° and D = 65 °C.

Table 2. $10^5 k_{2(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) values for different $[\text{DDTC}^-]$ concentrations at different temperatures

[Complex] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} , pH = 7.4, ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaClO₄

$10^3 \times [\text{Ligand}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	Temperature (°C)			
	50	55	60	65
1.0	0.39	0.5	0.66	0.85
2.0	0.71	0.91	1.12	1.49
3.0	0.97	1.20	1.54	2.04
4.0	1.10	1.45	1.85	2.32
5.0	1.27	1.61	2.10	2.63

Fig. 8. Eyring plot for the first path.

path is already complete. Thus there is no problem in calculating k_1 and k_2 .

The k_2 and K_E'' for the second path is calculated in a

Fig. 9. Plot of $\ln K_E'$ versus $1/T$ for the first path.

Fig. 10. Plot of $10^5 k_{2(\text{obs})}$ versus $[\text{ligand}]$, A = 50°, B = 55°, C = 60° and D = 65 °C.

Fig. 11. Plot of $1/k_{2(\text{obs})}$ against $1/[\text{ligand}]$, A = 50°, B = 55°, C = 60° and D = 65 °C.

manner similar to eq. (6) (Fig. 11) and data are collected in Table 3.

Based on the experimental findings, a two step interchange associative mechanism is proposed for the substitution process. In the first path, an outer sphere association complex is formed between the ligand and the two ruthenium(II) centers, which is stabilised by the H-bonding between the incoming ligand and the coordinated aqua

molecules. Now the interchange of the ligand from the outer sphere to the inner sphere occurs.

Effect of pH :

The reaction was studied at five different pH values. The k_{obs} values increases with increase in pH. With increasing pH, the proportion of the more reactive $[DDTC^-]$ form increases which accounts for the increase in rate with increasing pH. The complex also changes its form,

Fig. 12. Eyring plot for the second path.

Fig. 13. Plot of $\ln K_E''$ versus $1/T$ for the second path.

Table 3. The k_1 , K_E' , k_2 and K_E'' values

Temp. (°C)	$10^3 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	K_E' (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$10^5 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)	K_E'' (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
50	8.33	109	3.16	140
55	9.09	143	3.87	149
60	10.0	164	4.6	165
65	11.11	191	5.7	177

from aqua to hydroxo aqua and then to the oxobridged dimer. The hydroxo species is more reactive due to the well-known labilising effect of the -OH group via its π -bonding ability and strong electromeric effect.

Effect of temperature :

To study the effects of temperature the reaction was studied at four different temperatures for different [DDTC⁻] concentration and the results are listed in Tables 1 and 2. The activation parameters for both steps were evaluated from the linear Eyring plots (Figs. 8 and 12) giving values of $\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 14.14 \pm 0.96$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -241.59 \pm 2.93$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, $\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 31.88 \pm 1.91$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -232.94 \pm 5.79$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

The high negative values of ΔS^\ddagger are in support of the ligand participation in transition state in both the paths. The low ΔH^\ddagger values for both the paths suggests a more compact transition state than the starting complex which also corroborates the assumption of a ligand participating transition state.

Mechanism and conclusion :

The interaction of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDTC) with the ruthenium complex (1) at physiological pH proceeds through two distinct consecutive steps of substitution of aqua molecules ($k_1 \sim 10^{-3}$ s⁻¹ and $k_2 \sim 10^{-5}$ s⁻¹), each one step proceeds via an associative interchange activation. At this pH most of the ruthenium complexes

Table 4. The $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ and $10^5 k_{2(\text{obs})}$ values at different pHs

[1] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [ligand] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, temp. = 60 °C, ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄

pH	$10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^5 k_{2(\text{obs})}$ (s ⁻¹)
5.5	0.21	0.30
6.0	0.69	0.48
6.5	1.10	0.63
7.0	1.98	0.91
7.4	2.50	1.12

are oxidised to Ru^{III}; but this Ru^{II} complex is quite stable due its attached tap {2-(*m*-tolylazo)pyridine} ligands. At the outset of each path an outer sphere association complex is formed, which is stabilized through H-bonding, this is followed by an interchange from outer sphere to inner sphere complex. The outer sphere association equilibrium constants, a measure of the extent of H-bonding for each path at different temperatures are collected in Table 3. From the temperature dependence of the K_E' and K_E'' the thermodynamic parameters calculated (Fig. 9 and Fig. 13) are : $\Delta H_1^\circ = 32.26 \pm 3.27$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S_1^\circ = 139.24 \pm 9.6$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, $\Delta H_2^\circ = 13.94 \pm$

Fig. 14. Proposed mechanism for the interaction of [DDTC⁻] with complex (1).

0.99 kJ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S_2^\circ = 84.23 \pm 1.00 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. For both the paths ΔG° values calculated at all temperatures studied have a negative value which once again support in favour of the spontaneous formation of outer sphere association complex. The six membered structure of the product is also possible by the coordination of N and S atoms of [DDTC⁻] with the two Ru^{II} centers. But from the IR study it was confirmed that the two S atoms of [DDTC⁻] – react to form the six membered ring.

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